

pygopus family PHD finger 1 (PYGO1) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

pygopus family PHD finger 1 (PYGO1), recruitment permits β -catenin to transcriptionally activate WNT target genes. The presence of a PHD domain implicates PYGO proteins in a chromatin-related function. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 PYGO1 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of 7C_3 combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for PYGO1-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

^{*}Time behavioural study of 3-odr PYGO1 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of 71C_3 (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search down by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order PYGO1 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination,

then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. pygopus family PHD finger 1 (PYGO1)

WNT/Wingless signaling controls many fundamental processes during animal development and WNT transduction is mediated by the association of β -catenin with nuclear TCF DNA binding factors. Kramps et al. [4] report the identification of two segment polarity genes in *Drosophila*, i.e. legless (LGS) and PYGO, and show that they are required for WNT signal transduction at the level of nuclear β -catenin. LGS encodes BCL9, and they provide genetic/molecular evidence that these proteins exert their function by physically linking PYGO to β -catenin. The PYGO-BCL9 complex is a chromatin reader, the function of which relies on two ligand-binding surfaces of PYGO's PHD finger that anchor the histone H3 tail methylated at lysine 4 (H3K4me) with assistance from the BCL9 HD1 domain. Miller et al. [5] report the first use of fragment-based screening by NMR to identify small molecules that block protein-protein interactions by a PHD finger. Their results suggest that the recruitment of PYGO permits β -catenin to transcriptionally activate WNT target genes.

Thompson et al. [6] report the discovery of PYGO, whose mutant phenotypes specifically mimic loss-of-Wingless (Wg) signalling. PYGO is required for dTCF-mediated transcription, but not for Wg-induced stabilization of Arm and it is a nuclear protein that is found in a complex with Arm *in vivo*. Humans possess two PYGO proteins, both of which are required for TCF-mediated transcription in colorectal cancer cells. The presence of a PHD domain implicates PYGO proteins in a chromatin-related function, and the authors propose that they mediate chromatin access to TCF or Arm/ β -catenin.

Homeodomain proteins have been shown to play a major role in the development of various organisms. Schindler et al. [7] isolated a novel *Arabidopsis* homeodomain protein that had the capability to interact with a DNA motif. HAT3.1 does not contain a leucine zipper motif following the homeodomain and is further characterized by an N-terminal region that shares substantial sequence similarity with the maize homeodomain protein *Zmhox1a*. Within this conserved region, the presence of eight regularly spaced cysteine/histidine residues (Cys₄-His-Cys₃ motif) was observed that was reminiscent of other metal-binding domains. Being strongly evolutionary conserved, the authors proposed that this region represents a novel protein-motif which is denoted plant homeo-domain-finger (PHD-finger). Further, *in vitro* DNA binding studies demonstrated that HAT3.1 was capable of interacting with any DNA fragment larger than 100 bp and a deletion of the N-terminal PHD-finger domain completely abolished DNA binding, suggesting that this region might play an important functional role in

protein-protein or protein-DNA interaction. HAT3.1 mRNA was primarily detected in root tissue, implying a regulatory function of this protein in root development. The implications of PHD finger in chromatin-mediated transcriptional regulation have been documented in Aasland et al. [8].

In this research work, I present 3rd order combinations of PYGO1 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [9]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [9].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from

the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss

the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 PYGO1-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [10]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [11] and martinez implementation in Martinez [12] and Baudin et al. [13]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested PYGO1-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving PYGO1 were obtained from a full set of ${}^{71}C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2	191	48833	33097	15727	49025	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT2	214	45234	28842	7216	56378
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	218	3236	51191	53120	2659	DAAMI-PYGO1-WNT2	228	35434	22217	8095	17961
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP4	248	49907	20135	22408	46010	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	253	27760	37224	42160	22797
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	295	47321	21813	9500	57018	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	348	1924	32815	54426	36260
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	365	46893	25207	11837	39100	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	570	14118	6423	19469	36536
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2	590	20065	32145	31502	24399	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	593	19014	1524	25504	36744
LRP5-PYGO1-WNT2	598	6053	19908	2338	2607	DAAMI-PYGO1-SFRP4	632	42697	21965	12019	5353
PYGO1-WNT2-WNT2B	707	39634	53492	38813	24079	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2	817	38567	8350	5946	10554
CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7	838	55341	21851	12115	40132	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT3A	859	46424	26699	23831	49470
FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT4	880	37565	28874	6673	56916	FBXW2-PYGO1-SFRP4	895	48164	18463	9004	56766
CTBPI-PYGO1-WNT2	902	24919	8428	7477	7761	CCND1-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	906	40276	22490	8120	43281
DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7L1	959	51225	30853	10497	25266	CCND1-PYGO1-RHOU	1040	56164	34165	35225	53648
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2B	1041	14062	34049	32775	7169	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	1064	30070	1340	20277	52737
FBXW2-PYGO1-FBXW4	1225	51095	49445	9156	56717	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT3A	1243	46844	41378	10348	56667
FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	1288	22336	2406	8695	20479	JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	1341	24994	40582	4657	37476
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	1362	50934	48125	55357	25009	PYGO1-WNT2-WNT5A	1374	29615	29500	7763	11360
CTNNBIP1-PYGO1-WNT2	1475	25916	18667	8796	8023	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	1496	10929	38139	43067	17470
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT3A	1670	37660	30663	36831	4685	DKK1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	1693	11516	32448	36695	18729
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT2	1756	33028	17795	1917	9628	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PYGO1	1762	8717	41940	46022	26397
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2	1765	28859	12717	10912	10009	FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE2	1777	51565	50865	5489	56420
FZD5-PYGO1-TLE2	1787	4926	20017	5465	20177	CTBPI-PYGO1-WNT4	1792	40412	9281	9970	26271
FZD6-JUN-PYGO1	1799	8152	37586	49539	6795	JUN-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	1831	18378	16698	6395	19077
CTBPI-PYGO1-SFRP4	1847	16809	2399	14104	18544	FZD5-PYGO1-FBXW4	1870	26024	50283	20420	38032
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2B	1888	54480	51998	19913	52577	DKK1-PYGO1-FBXW4	1953	16029	50510	30614	10640
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2	1968	36688	49197	5995	43963	JUN-PYGO1-WNT2B	1971	11759	22992	23296	32538
CSNK1G1-JUN-PYGO1	2002	4879	55264	32395	18429	JUN-PYGO1-RHOU	2122	21105	6824	25993	11386
JUN-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2211	39190	16299	13477	38507	JUN-PYGO1-WNT5A	2273	30941	1607	4887	6388
FZD2-LEF1-PYGO1	2290	40489	23166	26380	24432	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	2296	35937	10116	9410	31529
DKK1-PYGO1-RHOU	2300	4971	25047	37502	11114	CCND1-PYGO1-SEN2	2354	25381	28894	27333	44018
DKK1-PYGO1-TLE2	2419	23834	49694	20745	27128	FBXW11-PYGO1-SEN2	2510	31734	49998	10856	40231
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT2	2594	6119	13281	49	48852	FZD1-PYGO1-SEN2	2614	7568	813	3128	19562
FRZB-PYGO1-SFRP4	2652	36390	1403	9283	23896	BTRC-GSK3A-PYGO1	2771	52085	53096	35408	47985
FZD5-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2870	23621	13839	25788	23143	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2B	2903	53947	46315	34453	44275
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	2904	37451	19332	29917	48436	FBXW11-PYGO1-TLE2	2906	44334	53969	2181	52786
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT3A	2944	11528	11111	13103	36306	EP300-PYGO1-WNT2	2948	43158	15314	8724	20816
CSNK1D-FGF4-PYGO1	2967	23307	41918	28164	3925	FZD5-PYGO1-WNT4	2980	4229	8238	13260	24709
CTBPI-PYGO1-TCF7	3004	9210	11537	8220	11898	CCND1-PYGO1-TLE2	3079	50182	49938	8787	45301
CTBPI-PYGO1-SEN2	3081	8819	2492	14648	22660	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	3094	24225	44587	43882	21321
DKK1-PYGO1-SFRP4	3105	19240	32988	43051	11763	DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	3118	7736	11350	8945	27577
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3	3128	434	1488	29	43589	FBXW11-PYGO1-SFRP4	3151	40355	44072	9884	48388
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	3193	33168	18183	17378	30931	PYGO1-WIF1-WNT4	3238	2703	55318	32252	32949
CCND1-PYGO1-FBXW4	3286	26986	41890	24897	52371	AES-FOXN1-PYGO1	3305	25455	24093	28905	5012
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3A	3330	4637	9706	492	45999	FZD1-PYGO1-WNT2	3364	25302	3943	1660	5188
FZD1-JUN-PYGO1	3370	32879	29253	28580	37224	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2B	3417	26749	22590	20939	16614
CCND3-PYGO1-WNT3A	3454	44362	41213	28500	14947	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-WNT2	3524	34440	54530	10724	18467
DVL2-PYGO1-TLE2	3562	38778	46616	3007	4918	CSNK1G1-PYGO1-TLE2	3565	24569	56894	5227	16188
FOSL1-JUN-PYGO1	3590	27459	38794	51790	55928	DVL2-PYGO1-FBXW4	3595	20330	55028	6420	42020
FZD7-PYGO1-WNT3A	3597	13080	6229	10048	9938	LRP5-PYGO1-SFRP4	3644	1525	13977	5563	18801
CTNNBIP1-PYGO1-SEN2	3739	6879	9216	12253	26261	CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	3805	54303	46961	29812	46238
FRZB-PYGO1-TLE2	3809	42613	27606	3105	9575	DVL2-PYGO1-SEN2	3834	9313	17069	10011	29581
GSK3B-PYGO1-TLE2	3889	10232	51499	31294	33743	CSNK1D-JUN-PYGO1	3934	1849	39438	23725	46933
AXIN1-MYC-PYGO1	3954	3444	10994	17667	24234	FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT3A	3985	37584	56193	14716	37160
LEF1-PYGO1-SFRP1	3992	3352	7797	117	11186	FOSL1-PYGO1-SFRP4	4009	35642	2304	16916	49861
FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	4132	14097	12408	18181	22475	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2B	4188	9498	24044	24964	53151
NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	4229	27445	40800	13988	7354	AES-JUN-PYGO1	4280	27713	29918	47174	22758
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2B	4284	33894	27397	24043	46041	LRP6-PYGO1-WIF1	4293	17363	23754	6785	4390
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2	4388	35884	6984	16968	53392	DVL2-PYGO1-TCF7L1	4435	40655	29622	11516	29181
FOSL1-PYGO1-SEN2	4461	29888	2317	13025	53543	DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7	4470	39048	22767	7968	11799
FZD5-PYGO1-RHOU	4574	8615	5925	32341	7083	PITX2-PYGO1-TLE2	4588	2003	47249	8274	54767
FZD5-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	4599	10851	8326	6893	16260	DAAMI-PYGO1-TLE1	4607	51419	32265	15738	19668
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP1	4616	49034	18235	22959	42446	FBXW11-PYGO1-TCF7L1	4731	49531	56943	14286	52062
DAAMI-JUN-PYGO1	4756	47637	25776	47368	4345	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-TCF7	4808	27076	33334	7691	16030
FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE1	4855	13029	28477	2137	56462	GSK3B-PYGO1-WNT2	4907	10086	14344	28902	33359

Table 1: Rankings of PYGO1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

RANKING @ t_1 USING HSIC - RBF											
3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2	7685	48218	45186	9095	12535	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT2	6632	47000	10921	10825	10660
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	35611	92	8244	34065	42310	DAAMI-PYGO1-WNT2	13220	45816	8644	1196	14447
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP4	7901	42981	32796	28660	4288	DKK1-PYGO1-SENP2	403	23098	9845	24707	36625
FBXW2-PYGO1-SENP2	5592	54522	7624	18559	15058	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	13399	522	43506	36219	51123
DAAMI-PYGO1-SENP2	7009	46420	6762	21944	29682	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	10181	579	35737	33610	43746
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2	3282	13742	6775	127	50868	FZD5-PYGO1-SENP2	864	25856	32614	26549	46981
LRP5-PYGO1-WNT2	24259	12625	15087	18812	33964	DAAMI-PYGO1-SFRP4	10758	46433	7217	48291	9239
PYGO1-WNT2-WNT2B	42713	30786	13433	45795	1718	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2	2310	29711	53695	989	52194
CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7	3994	53634	8088	23990	6794	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT3A	2014	38925	42108	33199	4343
FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT4	7669	38818	19627	43015	3643	FBXW2-PYGO1-SFRP4	6016	52622	9354	20433	4893
CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT2	7914	40190	53737	1881	54646	CCND1-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	8501	30855	32431	9221	12132
DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7L1	6113	49053	11325	35525	9242	CCND1-PYGO1-RHOU	5175	54648	29737	46772	20403
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2B	2010	10992	36338	13891	29481	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	7864	26771	50128	43544	15239
FBXW2-PYGO1-FBXW4	5992	55287	26603	3782	9116	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT3A	7391	48320	9248	34651	2524
FRZB-PYGO1-SENP2	334	16496	42795	31671	51686	JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	2091	9953	10078	26860	57045
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	15052	38950	15637	52389	3265	PYGO1-WNT2-WNT5A	36384	23157	25066	7716	16105
CTNNB1P1-PYGO1-WNT2	20950	23080	54816	1243	54421	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	15268	3842	31367	43633	53074
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT3A	1315	30284	30530	24495	19085	DKK1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2316	814	35496	27049	25451
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT2	6832	31920	27128	7953	48179	CTNNB1P1-JUN-PYGO1	41135	2896	47437	45143	51706
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2	3462	16415	43751	3201	35160	FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE2	6212	55715	1956	16260	24385
FZD5-PYGO1-TLE2	4104	5653	37820	25448	57153	CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT4	22742	44655	41099	39815	48059
FZD6-JUN-PYGO1	35697	277	641	50698	33247	JUN-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	3487	15500	27418	13894	51869
CTBP1-PYGO1-SFRP4	22918	27814	51439	38327	43332	FZD5-PYGO1-FBXW4	8568	40214	29428	9395	56877
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2B	7490	53715	924	4743	16840	DKK1-PYGO1-FBXW4	4015	24648	4205	73	53593
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2	13085	22818	21507	4205	23661	JUN-PYGO1-WNT2B	2703	20164	23828	23294	38517
CSNK1G1-JUN-PYGO1	17775	1546	36260	46060	22759	JUN-PYGO1-RHOU	3507	2626	38630	48273	44356
JUN-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2998	25012	36064	35492	46418	JUN-PYGO1-WNT5A	9776	20912	9445	6655	56641
FZD2-LEF1-PYGO1	19320	30354	33523	35934	37423	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	4646	17601	54904	1115	45855
DKK1-PYGO1-RHOU	594	8755	12396	40458	43195	CCND1-PYGO1-SENP2	2887	16723	33585	4220	12776
LEF1-PYGO1-TLE2	1493	17701	42910	17294	57025	FBXW11-PYGO1-SENP2	882	19979	26917	15962	25523
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2	4130	36760	36544	4175	29233	FZD1-PYGO1-SENP2	2237	14486	13479	4706	37678
FRZB-PYGO1-SFRP4	2953	27146	15142	30999	39478	BTRC-GSK3A-PYGO1	16077	51303	28870	23885	34429
FZD5-PYGO1-TCF7L1	552	22883	43339	19418	51934	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2B	4500	49840	12312	25574	14068
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	2480	27771	5674	47549	30280	FBXW11-PYGO1-TLE2	3570	44556	20858	19771	39583
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT3A	18087	2223	36690	1889	26351	EP300-PYGO1-WNT2	5709	43420	44821	441	34191
CSNK1D-FGF4-PYGO1	35224	24194	35705	42726	4974	FZD5-PYGO1-WNT4	12619	9688	49504	15069	50337
CTBP1-PYGO1-TCF7	12120	36550	3309	22441	35094	CCND1-PYGO1-TLE2	2708	46475	14041	11551	36187
CTBP1-PYGO1-SENP2	14535	11602	42803	9594	47507	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	33906	17235	3856	45519	18398
DKK1-PYGO1-SFRP4	3408	7708	23449	34970	34048	DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	9260	4892	51202	277	17819
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3	8116	6747	37915	10868	26227	FBXW11-PYGO1-SFRP4	3371	25915	424	42974	31841
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	9179	35935	48383	28960	14143	PYGO1-WIF1-WNT4	30659	11937	27320	45398	3025
CCND1-PYGO1-FBXW4	5824	27098	17674	13615	16815	AES-FOXN1-PYGO1	4657	24703	43459	42184	24604
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3A	7948	34410	45811	27590	17447	FZD1-PYGO1-WNT2	8801	28775	15560	1399	50819
FZD1-JUN-PYGO1	46076	19069	9867	46865	48594	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2B	3505	12360	4064	28390	55537
CCND3-PYGO1-WNT3A	782	47470	16204	30209	9636	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-WNT2	6052	32583	28770	2461	39536
DVL2-PYGO1-TLE2	8563	43181	37961	17796	56882	CSNK1G1-PYGO1-TLE2	21495	24434	29013	7562	53728
FOSL1-JUN-PYGO1	39670	8443	35133	55401	48823	DVL2-PYGO1-FBXW4	15883	30156	604	9016	45692
FZD7-PYGO1-WNT3A	2200	3030	44689	22869	39525	LRP5-PYGO1-SFRP4	14664	1251	37823	41590	26535
CTNNB1P1-PYGO1-SENP2	8077	5298	52208	9813	41948	CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	10623	47122	16194	21979	4501
FRZB-PYGO1-TLE2	3510	45630	22284	32164	57136	DVL2-PYGO1-SENP2	3166	806	29432	11396	29074
GSK3B-PYGO1-TLE2	1511	1087	42710	14437	57121	CSNK1D-JUN-PYGO1	46732	424	46278	41608	30058
AXIN1-MYC-PYGO1	33645	8460	51922	49242	34352	FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT3A	5958	23716	24819	17645	5707
LEF1-PYGO1-SFRP1	8248	25313	16956	27035	35434	FOSL1-PYGO1-SFRP4	3428	32371	44049	49180	33552
FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	6165	13829	40997	17174	24514	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2B	4892	4674	16682	35879	52932
NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	7759	3583	13307	7257	24124	AES-JUN-PYGO1	25084	9408	7447	50510	20969
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2B	5074	27177	16095	15562	27187	LRP6-PYGO1-WIF1	40589	27373	31407	1058	42246
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2	2834	38294	45106	1581	41784	DVL2-PYGO1-TCF7L1	4022	45893	41755	25284	37685
FOSL1-PYGO1-SENP2	977	13985	43848	13391	28612	DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7	1729	42769	4631	5543	14266
FZD5-PYGO1-RHOU	543	3213	11602	49189	47416	PITX2-PYGO1-TLE2	1782	35079	27236	39307	56772
FZD5-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	13164	6884	38119	28521	55716	DAAMI-PYGO1-TLE1	9367	40988	3088	5163	19658
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP1	7909	44664	37002	6160	22267	FBXW11-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2771	39588	19054	11993	11919
DAAMI-JUN-PYGO1	35403	45052	14876	50189	5673	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-TCF7	4497	22038	26026	17251	48738
FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE1	11243	2157	3112	11981	5521	GSK3B-PYGO1-WNT2	4395	4042	49269	2154	52107

Table 2: Rankings of PYGO1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of WNT-PYGO1-X combinations

Kramps et al. [4] indicate that TCF and β -catenin function in a tetrapartite complex with LGS/BCL9 and PYGO to transcriptionally activate target genes in response to

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2	23571	36410	15616	2053	54902	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT2	22809	29745	16419	7178	38040
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	20453	50366	17707	8188	42484	DAAMI-PYGO1-WNT2	11655	42330	15885	7995	42320
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP4	6028	42645	2289	1001	55845	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	5320	8965	25659	16677	34823
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	19176	47463	19297	20507	39832	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	22701	20169	18383	5021	52969
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	10224	2416	14099	12136	24858	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	1610	17601	24757	13846	37085
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2	3006	20828	19259	10946	32234	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	10582	54199	15471	9662	50406
LRP5-PYGO1-WNT2	6676	12359	19432	21720	43580	DAAMI-PYGO1-SFRP4	12825	5259	14739	27176	39944
PYGO1-WNT2-WNT2B	35098	23545	34784	49087	46216	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2	12262	22169	15532	4607	50768
CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7	18122	45572	2446	2027	55938	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT3A	39080	19013	56205	51729	13572
FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT4	6048	35274	8914	13383	40180	FBXW2-PYGO1-SFRP4	22052	24720	4613	5903	54788
CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT2	20153	27678	2537	9397	33838	CCND1-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	5279	1741	18699	16570	29343
DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7L1	37114	50690	39761	33545	3030	CCND1-PYGO1-RHOU	43775	56261	50329	56095	7953
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2B	54188	35764	37921	46266	24833	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	52932	56977	53771	37472	14726
FBXW2-PYGO1-FBXW4	35105	32258	52561	51292	2367	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT3A	52031	31884	46340	31823	2792
FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	11932	6986	25367	12616	52422	JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	3800	11209	18229	255	32111
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	25910	36673	28134	15173	40843	PYGO1-WNT2-WNT5A	38189	30159	29176	50070	44803
CTNNB1P1-PYGO1-WNT2	11459	19288	18921	4735	9712	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	13879	27252	8058	10543	55180
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT3A	49429	22863	28934	47297	24196	DKK1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	53013	53567	39949	56715	29970
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT2	24731	1948	7444	10308	48870	CTNNB1P1-JUN-PYGO1	14511	20205	9590	1997	56057
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2	1313	6988	26283	14105	56504	FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE2	32326	13530	50413	46764	9323
FZD5-PYGO1-TLE2	43027	104	46448	43876	24737	CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT4	27649	26968	22166	2301	29150
FZD6-JUN-PYGO1	660	283	18899	19152	55094	JUN-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	39968	7155	33471	32607	20833
CTBP1-PYGO1-SFRP4	18530	26668	2815	1299	30332	FZD5-PYGO1-FBXW4	39183	2104	46072	43193	2921
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2B	33541	53563	42544	44866	11547	DKK1-PYGO1-FBXW4	51614	42906	37164	38683	33819
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2	23628	3600	14621	12236	45387	JUN-PYGO1-WNT2B	784	29200	21789	1189	45268
CSNK1G1-JUN-PYGO1	39719	47416	54841	47973	10949	JUN-PYGO1-RHOU	3266	37143	23419	11201	38259
JUN-PYGO1-TCF7L1	4196	41759	27014	26374	34930	JUN-PYGO1-WNT5A	2460	21997	22687	2953	49677
FZD2-LEF1-PYGO1	39966	1605	48301	38150	15979	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	47297	50999	30260	50806	4015
DKK1-PYGO1-RHOU	52268	16276	32787	34998	26390	CCND1-PYGO1-SEN2	9363	55936	5775	22711	48701
LEF1-PYGO1-TLE2	53371	13490	36793	44944	18357	FBXW11-PYGO1-SEN2	23322	1344	12785	8511	39644
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2	17290	10437	14509	19069	34734	FZD1-PYGO1-SEN2	17605	57130	8602	23919	43562
FRZB-PYGO1-SFRP4	19646	20211	10524	5314	31613	BTRC-GSK3A-PYGO1	40306	12238	50108	55258	7556
FZD5-PYGO1-TCF7L1	39929	19214	31569	49425	9668	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2B	33592	20824	41585	55101	2315
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	49601	24278	44028	43212	12272	FBXW11-PYGO1-TLE2	33225	36548	35122	52970	13629
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT3A	35451	32587	46161	49351	14826	EP300-PYGO1-WNT2	31940	56694	45844	45742	12882
CSNK1D-FGF4-PYGO1	41090	20740	34158	34168	20857	FZD5-PYGO1-WNT4	15278	10463	12217	3358	53540
CTBP1-PYGO1-TCF7	19167	24468	5531	3011	33571	CCND1-PYGO1-TLE2	38969	17016	52496	38112	384
CTBP1-PYGO1-SEN2	10240	25052	9151	4681	32852	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	17301	5414	8956	6791	9863
DKK1-PYGO1-SFRP4	5555	14281	20084	18507	23471	DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	38631	6548	43841	56224	38207
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3	16493	40318	11960	27230	25603	FBXW11-PYGO1-SFRP4	19547	42729	11935	6272	45795
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	2188	42426	19263	4130	25766	PYGO1-WIF1-WNT4	35126	29183	31527	51724	48035
CCND1-PYGO1-FBXW4	51130	15106	54885	56151	1320	AES-FOXN1-PYGO1	13627	21324	3166	21211	26154
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3A	40621	17131	45161	29919	31440	FZD1-PYGO1-WNT2	18743	55194	11811	3018	31667
FZD1-JUN-PYGO1	10842	9463	23552	17495	34735	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2B	44906	34928	41610	52546	6348
CCND3-PYGO1-WNT3A	51433	27320	30354	36390	39641	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-WNT2	27842	10862	10937	6962	53007
DVL2-PYGO1-TLE2	34256	44308	42625	42719	3422	CSNK1G1-PYGO1-TLE2	17136	9155	11518	17890	32040
FOSL1-JUN-PYGO1	35100	56491	39744	42645	28344	DVL2-PYGO1-FBXW4	29729	33444	33783	33618	40149
FZD7-PYGO1-WNT3A	1165	50482	26897	25768	53340	LRP5-PYGO1-SFRP4	2300	55858	7523	22759	51715
CTNNB1P1-PYGO1-SEN2	21191	36983	19971	3965	11871	CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	39036	11286	54703	55124	1216
FRZB-PYGO1-TLE2	45842	21383	45458	51288	1668	DVL2-PYGO1-SEN2	26270	14793	24368	13556	8825
GSK3B-PYGO1-TLE2	55303	43455	31052	48879	8231	CSNK1D-JUN-PYGO1	24772	39437	27678	10274	47704
AXIN1-MYC-PYGO1	4066	39692	3553	5774	48217	FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT3A	39947	53781	36004	52889	15695
LEF1-PYGO1-SFRP1	53359	2338	48778	30849	55971	FOSL1-PYGO1-SFRP4	39720	40936	40202	47288	2631
FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	37686	56136	39369	37595	23150	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2B	12441	11961	5832	1148	30998
NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	7875	21489	20941	18370	48652	AES-JUN-PYGO1	20909	15200	3792	28252	30883
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2B	55854	50198	30897	43016	651	LRP6-PYGO1-WIF1	44508	17042	34865	29362	9716
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2	7561	33096	13153	14050	44943	DVL2-PYGO1-TCF7L1	30408	40479	30117	35926	43261
FOSL1-PYGO1-SEN2	48594	56124	49849	56650	18878	DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7	20090	6405	17388	23697	54109
FZD5-PYGO1-RHOU	43941	53488	41361	43989	27808	PITX2-PYGO1-TLE2	19850	10379	18180	6093	40940
FZD5-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	10744	49408	12251	7758	51542	DAAMI-PYGO1-TLE1	11821	6611	9646	28349	35623
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP1	47797	1211	51402	34391	8554	FBXW11-PYGO1-TCF7L1	34205	54669	45848	48836	12237
DAAMI-JUN-PYGO1	10734	4256	13652	16493	54555	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-TCF7	15569	3364	11248	16573	53352
FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE1	24866	43447	6766	10408	47911	GSK3B-PYGO1-WNT2	7165	34491	27181	12830	44756

Table 3: Rankings of PYGO1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

WNT signals. Using in situ hybridization, Schwab et al. [14] examined expression of three WNT7B (Kispert et al. [15]), WNT11 (Majumdar et al. [16]) and WNT9B (Carroll et al. [17]) genes in PYGO mutants. They found that all three genes showed similar expression patterns in PYGO2^{+/+} and PYGO1/PYGO2 double-mutant kid-

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2	37911	51075	18835	18238	32015	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT2	26757	35403	7450	10247	25277
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	18955	10082	6546	24602	4336	DAAMI-PYGO1-WNT2	15041	15718	53732	52345	3587
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP4	52920	430	3267	28973	14789	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	44254	18975	35893	25046	32000
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	3761	16157	15508	5360	43710	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	21220	21257	46978	36871	44319
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	36499	23008	51614	13246	37650	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	8462	12690	54986	11759	6706
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2	42416	8108	38068	18037	24994	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	22699	16430	36618	55374	27834
LRP5-PYGO1-WNT2	51485	24721	56036	55929	7057	DAAMI-PYGO1-SFRP4	11653	17667	55752	44844	766
PYGO1-WNT2-WNT2B	23785	7527	40262	615	38247	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2	30343	41529	16576	38011	56049
CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7	31140	36909	39378	11729	1261	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT3A	37702	16739	21907	35980	8685
FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT4	52436	10894	44161	20796	21790	FBXW2-PYGO1-SFRP4	34135	38425	8299	14402	25325
CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT2	47604	10878	21289	22983	27237	CCND1-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	48807	34948	10049	19018	5626
DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7L1	41604	24817	49648	27162	11744	CCND1-PYGO1-RHOU	31251	50423	11785	10303	41620
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2B	9922	1845	49860	25488	36909	KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A	30698	50067	9324	3950	37622
FBXW2-PYGO1-FBXW4	20026	17553	40625	37294	35637	FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT3A	12666	21939	42752	33609	33918
FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	29413	11451	18530	12785	54338	JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	39043	10881	55054	5405	2750
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	1105	3178	49390	42434	50732	PYGO1-WNT2-WNT5A	30225	31821	37178	9770	16977
CTNNB1P1-PYGO1-WNT2	31287	19283	31230	15275	34109	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	19004	24107	54656	40210	53966
DKK1-PYGO1-WNT3A	8005	22192	47473	28811	30935	DKK1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	9598	1548	49564	17605	29906
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT2	19032	54400	43349	2340	25655	CTNNB1P1-JUN-PYGO1	4159	56180	29815	12792	54068
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2	12652	11545	10776	30241	14535	FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE2	18276	10805	43721	26571	21881
FZD5-PYGO1-TLE2	17963	9519	7060	49788	52343	CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT4	31272	3069	22436	8609	40251
FZD6-JUN-PYGO1	29460	27936	11277	3143	19348	JUN-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	5851	40432	40855	24827	37779
CTBP1-PYGO1-SFRP4	46712	2252	5947	13272	50543	FZD5-PYGO1-FBXW4	12016	52502	13925	51717	7784
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2B	38516	3021	34825	23473	34676	DKK1-PYGO1-FBXW4	9296	627	49445	23201	34684
FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2	23794	22676	3852	35790	5627	JUN-PYGO1-WNT2B	8806	9304	56999	30033	36730
CSNK1G1-JUN-PYGO1	15049	21562	26708	38509	8167	JUN-PYGO1-RHOU	21520	15769	56551	7365	30064
JUN-PYGO1-TCF7L1	1804	12583	2154	1965	6968	JUN-PYGO1-WNT5A	5773	12825	7216	47792	6321
FZD2-LEF1-PYGO1	40471	18917	3283	2629	9623	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2	9587	46756	39612	28530	26972
DKK1-PYGO1-RHOU	8459	21111	52092	22523	40765	CCND1-PYGO1-SEN2	45414	14428	41298	27143	50349
DKK1-PYGO1-TLE2	9018	1581	49238	27229	33347	FBXW11-PYGO1-SEN2	12847	15596	9467	25359	836
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT2	5583	56394	56306	53464	2168	FZD1-PYGO1-SEN2	21407	10831	17596	49929	54668
FRZB-PYGO1-SFRP4	26489	22059	27398	6626	32548	BTRC-GSK3A-PYGO1	11357	49908	16814	7464	44597
FZD5-PYGO1-TCF7L1	14133	53628	24856	49609	44493	CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2B	24755	26859	7596	34705	10674
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B	18735	48555	26440	4828	14893	FBXW11-PYGO1-TLE2	39018	26680	202	54003	31562
DVL2-PYGO1-WNT3A	43701	24035	15691	38022	9753	EP300-PYGO1-WNT2	48602	27784	3033	4313	26421
CSNK1D-FGF4-PYGO1	53782	7577	1845	21026	56561	FZD5-PYGO1-WNT4	33763	36551	23826	53334	40907
CTBP1-PYGO1-TCF7	40858	54704	26171	14585	52039	CCND1-PYGO1-TLE2	39532	13515	4655	29162	17412
CTBP1-PYGO1-SEN2	41481	1878	11331	10754	48179	FRAT1-JUN-PYGO1	444	16817	15763	18220	54420
DKK1-PYGO1-SFRP4	26781	9694	35257	18705	4781	DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2	5303	19804	36529	40903	23672
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3	563	17584	32269	5434	16351	FBXW11-PYGO1-SFRP4	12147	14585	8927	56629	7775
DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	31758	28937	44898	49405	29636	PYGO1-WIF1-WNT4	26212	511	30152	3118	21443
CCND1-PYGO1-FBXW4	35324	25017	23988	14824	30764	AES-FOXN1-PYGO1	35515	11455	12087	9945	40065
LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3A	5198	45927	54006	20564	20342	FZD1-PYGO1-WNT2	30747	48208	38155	37601	46531
FZD1-JUN-PYGO1	9757	33666	34886	20936	41863	FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2B	54026	32990	8193	30281	7606
CCND3-PYGO1-WNT3A	54519	5890	27106	31847	16248	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-WNT2	1343	46514	39128	51687	744
DVL2-PYGO1-TLE2	42763	978	18341	7309	13510	CSNK1G1-PYGO1-TLE2	6707	43365	50722	55108	11091
FOSL1-JUN-PYGO1	5957	1126	50697	48578	45721	DVL2-PYGO1-FBXW4	32635	27756	7653	5247	14171
FZD7-PYGO1-WNT3A	9804	27532	53059	23345	3373	LRP5-PYGO1-SFRP4	45030	27891	53379	55325	19522
CTNNB1P1-PYGO1-SEN2	581	25298	24837	51245	555	CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7L1	35976	22054	18869	34556	8370
FRZB-PYGO1-TLE2	48355	41544	1704	26733	9591	DVL2-PYGO1-SEN2	14808	48953	14702	8599	8489
GSK3B-PYGO1-TLE2	45720	21780	28500	51103	32591	CSNK1D-JUN-PYGO1	5673	24084	17393	28564	30653
AXIN1-MYC-PYGO1	41385	17844	40336	19014	33077	FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT3A	50959	38129	6742	53728	35651
LEF1-PYGO1-SFRP1	18494	15780	53812	19282	33414	FOSL1-PYGO1-SFRP4	7741	47499	41066	27990	35705
FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A	54346	46674	9496	2030	10423	FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2B	51456	15465	7011	36572	28842
NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	20464	41550	50440	17275	1201	AES-JUN-PYGO1	26858	20252	24865	16987	7058
FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2B	48843	42665	23416	10041	50436	LRP6-PYGO1-WIF1	27947	43528	52323	46450	25041
KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2	13378	22295	20108	4275	50342	DVL2-PYGO1-TCF7L1	38991	24840	9195	31468	13833
FOSL1-PYGO1-SEN2	8313	34088	39552	17125	42244	DAAMI-PYGO1-TCF7	2821	4370	44449	45542	53043
FZD5-PYGO1-RHOU	25736	53449	15	51301	38823	PITX2-PYGO1-TLE2	4242	25999	8726	47004	18848
FZD5-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1	33572	37375	40307	52352	16417	DAAMI-PYGO1-TLE1	16729	17870	54922	41397	43491
CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP1	39177	33994	12673	19976	11482	FBXW11-PYGO1-TCF7L1	48695	2355	12409	55468	29411
DAAMI-JUN-PYGO1	13317	22174	38416	18316	30987	CSNK2A1-PYGO1-TCF7	22495	14182	9919	4915	3730
FBXW2-PYGO1-TLE1	43211	29137	8236	21037	44316	GSK3B-PYGO1-WNT2	3320	3950	16597	47246	787

Table 4: Rankings of PYGO1-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

neys. They also showed a reduced number of tips (WNT11-positive) per surface area in the PYGO1/PYGO2 double-homozygous mutants. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the WNT family along with PYGO1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2, DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2,

LRP5-PYGO1-WNT2, PYGO1-WNT2-WNT2B, FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT4, CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT2, DKK1-PYGO1-WNT2B, CTNNBIP1-PYGO1-WNT2, DKK1-PYGO1-WNT3A, DVL2-PYGO1-WNT2, FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2, FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2B, FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT2, LEF1-PYGO1-WNT2, KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2B, DVL2-PYGO1-WNT3A, LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3, LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3A, CCND3-PYGO1-WNT3A, FZD7-PYGO1-WNT3A, FRAT1-PYGO1-WNT3A, NLK-PYGO1-WNT2, FZD8-PYGO1-WNT2B, KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT2, FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT2, DAAM1-PYGO1-WNT2, JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A, FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2, CCND1-PYGO1-WNT3A, KREMEN1-PYGO1-WNT3A, FBXW2-PYGO1-WNT3A, PYGO1-WNT2-WNT5A, CTBP1-PYGO1-WNT4, JUN-PYGO1-WNT2B, JUN-PYGO1-WNT5A, FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2, CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2B, EP300-PYGO1-WNT2, FZD5-PYGO1-WNT4, DIXDC1-PYGO1-WNT2, PYGO1-WIF1-WNT4, FZD1-PYGO1-WNT2, FRZB-PYGO1-WNT2B, CSNK2A1-PYGO1-WNT2, FBXW11-PYGO1-WNT3A, FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2B and GSK3B-PYGO1-WNT2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of TCF/LEF-PYGO1-X combinations

Mosimann et al. [18] address how β -catenin copes with chromatin regulation to turn on WNT target genes? Once in the nucleus, β -catenin interacts with members of the DNA-binding T cell factor/lymphoid enhancer factor (TCF/LEF) family proteins to form a bipartite transcription factor. Giese et al. [19] provide evidence that DNA binding by the HMG domain of LEF1 involves primarily minor groove contacts and induces a bend of approximately 130 in the DNA helix. LEF1 and TCF1 are DNA-binding proteins that play important regulatory roles in organogenesis and thymocyte differentiation. Love et al. [20] report the solution structure of a complex of the LEF1 HMG domain and adjacent basic region with its cognate DNA. Thus, Mosimann et al. [18] state that TCFs induce strong DNA bending following binding for example, LEF1 induces an extreme 130° kink. Finally, Xie et al. [21] measured colocalization of WNT-related proteins and found that TCF7L1 exhibited increased colocalization with PYGO1 and FRA1/FOSL1. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the TCF family along with PYGO1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7, DAAM1-PYGO1-TCF7L1, JUN-PYGO1-TCF7L1, FZD5-PYGO1-TCF7L1, CTBP1-PYGO1-TCF7, DIXDC1-PYGO1-TCF7L1, DKK1-PYGO1-TCF7L1, CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7L1, DVL2-PYGO1-TCF7L1, DAAM1-PYGO1-TCF7, FBXW11-PYGO1-TCF7L1 and CSNK2A1-PYGO1-TCF7. Also, looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for LEF1 along with PYGO1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FZD2-LEF1-PYGO1, LEF1-PYGO1-WNT2, LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3, LEF1-PYGO1-WNT3A and LEF1-PYGO1-SFRP1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of AXIN/MYC-PYGO1-X combinations

Lin et al. [22] show that AXIN2 and c-MYC (downstream target genes of β -catenin), and molecular markers of cardiac hypertrophy, were reactivated in PYGO1-overexpressing transgenic (PYGO1-TG) mice. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following

combinations for AXIN1 and MYC along with PYGO1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AXIN1-MYC-PYGO1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of FOSL1-PYGO1-X combinations

Xie et al. [21] measured colocalization of WNT-related proteins and found that TCF7L1 exhibited increased colocalization with PYGO1 and FOS like 1, AP-1 transcription factor subunit (FRA1/FOSL1). Zhang et al. [23] demonstrate that WNT3A administration activated by WNT/ β -catenin signalling and directly activated the transcription of FRA1, which played a crucial role in the glioma aggressiveness and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). Not much is known about the connection between PYGO and FOSL1, however, looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for FOSL1 along with PYGO1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-JUN-PYGO1, FOSL1-PYGO1-SEN2, FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2, FOSL1-PYGO1-SFRP4 and FOSL1-PYGO1-WNT2B. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of CCND-PYGO1-X combinations

Katoh and Katoh [24] indicate that nuclear β -catenin is complexed with TCF/LEF HMG-box transcription factors, Legless (BCL-9/9L) and PYGO (PYGO-1/2) to activate transcription of CCND1, MYC, FGF18 and FGF20 genes for the cell-fate determination. In colon cancer, Tetsu and McCormick [25] show that β -catenin activates transcription from the CCND1 promoter, and that sequences within the promoter that are related to consensus TCF/LEF-binding sites are necessary for activation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CCND family along with PYGO1, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2, CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP4, CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7, CCND3-JUN-PYGO1, CCND1-PYGO1-FBXW4, CCND3-PYGO1-WNT3A, CCND1-PYGO1-SFRP1, CCND1-PYGO1-WNT3A, CCND1-PYGO1-SLC9A3R1, CCND1-PYGO1-RHOA, CCND1-PYGO1-SEN2, CCND1-PYGO1-WNT2B, CCND1-PYGO1-TLE2 and CCND1-PYGO1-TCF7L1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of PYGO1 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the PYGO1, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For PYGO1, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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